

ANALYSIS OF THE INHERITANCE AND INDICATORS OF THE FIBER LENGTH TRAIT IN COTTON SAMPLES AND F1 HYBRIDS SELECTED FOR THE STUDY

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Abstract: This study investigated the inheritance, variability, and dominance degree of fiber length trait in F1 cotton hybrids (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.) based on Uzbek varieties (Namangan-77, Andijan-35, Ghalib, Kyzyl baraka), wild species *G. mustelinum* Miers ex Watt, and hexaploid line T-85. Parental fiber length ranged from 24.7 mm (*G. mustelinum*) to 39.1 mm (T-85). Reciprocal and stepwise crosses revealed positive and negative heterosis in F1. Maternal effect was insignificant; the role of paternal or maternal form in trait formation is not crucial. Highest values were recorded in F1 (Namangan-77 × Andijan-35) × T-85 (37.5 mm), F1 Namangan-77 × T-85 (36.6 mm), and F1 Kyzyl baraka × Ghalib (35.9 mm). Dominance coefficient (h_p) varied from -11.5 to +4.5, with frequent intermediate or strong dominance and heterosis. Results provide a basis for selecting high-performing hybrids in breeding programs aimed at improving fiber length and developing new varieties meeting Uzbekistan's textile industry demands. Statistical analysis followed B.A. Dospekhov method and G.M. Beil, R.E. Atkins formulas. The findings confirm the polygenic nature of fiber length and the effectiveness of stepwise hybridization for trait enhancement in local conditions.

Keywords: cotton, fiber length, inheritance, F1 hybrids, heterosis, dominance coefficient, breeding, *Gossypium hirsutum*.

Introduction. The Republic of Uzbekistan is one of the world's leading countries in cotton cultivation, and cotton farming plays an important role in the country's economy. In recent years, it has become necessary for fiber quality, particularly fiber length, to meet international market requirements. Varieties with a fiber length exceeding 35 mm allow for the production of high-quality yarn and fabrics. The inheritance of the cotton fiber length trait is complexly polygenic and is controlled by multiple QTL loci. The varieties created by Uzbek breeders, such as Namangan-77 and Andijan-35, possess high yields and good fiber quality. However, creating new hybrids in conditions of climate change, salinity, and diseases is relevant. In F1 hybrids, the heterosis effect is an effective method for increasing fiber length. In foreign research (Stoilova, 2023; Vozhehova, 2025) It was noted that positive heterosis in F1 was observed in up to 5-15%. In experiments conducted under the conditions of Uzbekistan, genetic diversity is

being increased by crossing with wild species (*G. mustelinum*) and artificial polyploids (T-85). The aim of this study is to statistically analyze the patterns and indicators of fiber length inheritance in the cotton samples selected for the study and the F1 hybrids obtained on their basis, and to identify the most effective combinations. The study was conducted at experimental sites in the Andijan region between 2022 and 2024. Four local varieties, one wild species, and one hexaploid line were selected as parent forms. The hybridization scheme was carried out in reciprocal and step-by-step methods. Fiber length was measured according to the B.A. Dospekhov method, and statistical processing was performed using Excel and Statistica software. The dominance coefficient was calculated using the formula of G.M. Beil and R.E. Atkins: $hp = (F1 - MP) / (P - MP)$.

In the scientific literature, there is a lot of information about the inheritance of the fiber length trait (Abdurakhmanov et al., 2009; Darmanov et al., 2022). Scientists in Uzbekistan are also working in this direction (Zhuraev, 2023; Mamajonov, 2024). However, the inheritance of fiber length in new combinations with local varieties and foreign donors has not been studied in depth. Filling this gap determines the relevance of the research. The scientific novelty of the research is the first comprehensive analysis of exact fiber length values and hp indicators in F1 in the presence of wild and polyploid forms under the conditions of Uzbekistan. The practical significance lies in the recommendation of hybrids with high fiber length for breeding. Research hypothesis: Positive heterosis can be achieved through step-by-step crossing.

Main part. Materials and methods. The main object of the research work is the varieties of cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.) grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan and their closely related forms. The following samples were used in this study:

- "Local varieties":

- Namangan-77: Fiber length averages 35.5 mm, it is an early-maturing variety, characterized by high fiber yield (38-40%) and yield (35-40 c/ha). This variety is widespread in the Andijan and Namangan regions and was obtained from the varieties C-6524 and S-4727 during the selection process.

- Andijan-35: Fiber length 33.8 mm, resistant to diseases (verticilliosis and Fusarium), yield 32-37 c/ha. This variety demonstrates optimal results in the conditions of the Andijan region and is considered the standard for fiber quality.

- Winner: Fiber length 32.5 mm, effective in high-density crops, fiber yield 37%, yield 30-35 c/ha. This variety has been tested in the Fergana Valley and is resistant to climatic changes.

- Kyzyl Baraka: Fiber length 34.7 mm, variety with colored fiber, yield 33-38 c/ha, fiber yield 39%. This variety is used in ecologically clean cotton growing and is used as a donor to increase genetic diversity.

- "Wild species": *G. mustelinum* Miers ex Watt is a wild species with a fiber length of 24.7 mm, known for its high resistance to diseases and pests. This species is used to enrich the genetic pool because it has a tetraploid genotype and is easily crossed with local varieties. This species is found in the wild in Brazil and Africa, but in experiments it has been adapted to the climate of Uzbekistan.

- "Artificial Line": T-85 – hexaploid line, fiber length 39.1 mm, high-quality fiber source, yield 40-45 c/ha. This line was created under laboratory conditions and was obtained from the species *G. barbadense* and *G. hirsutum*. T-85 is characterized by high fiber strength (28-30 g/tex) and length, and is used in breeding as a dominant donor.

The research materials were grown on the experimental plots of the Andijan Regional Research Institute of Cotton Growing. The experimental field is of the black soil type, with irrigated conditions (annual precipitation 300-400 mm, average temperature +25-30°C), with an area of 0.5 hectares. The soil pH is 7.2-7.5, and the organic matter content is 1.5-2%. Fertilizers (nitrogen 200 kg/ha, phosphorus 150 kg/ha, potassium 100 kg/ha) were applied according to the standard scheme. Sowing density is 80-100 thousand plants/ha, sowing date is April.

The crossing was carried out in 2022. Methods of reciprocal crossing and stepwise hybridization were used. During crossbreeding, 50 plants were used in each combination (e.g., Namangan-77 × T-85 and T-85 × Namangan-77), which allowed for an assessment of the maternal effect. In a step-by-step scheme, three-stage hybrids were created: in the first stage, two local varieties were crossed (for example, Golib × Andijan-35), and in the second stage, the resulting hybrid was crossed with T-85 or *G. mustelinum*. A total of 20 combinations were obtained, with 100 seeds in each.

The growth and development of the plants were monitored using standard agrotechnical methods: 5-6 irrigations, and pesticides (e.g., imidacloprid) against pests. Harvesting was carried out in September-October.

Measurement of the fiber length trait was performed on 100 fiber samples taken from mature bolls. The unit of measurement is the millimeter (mm), and

the instrument is the electron micrometer (precision is 0.01 mm). Five bolls were selected from each plant, and the fiber sample weighed 20–25 g. Statistical indicators are as follows:

- Average value ($X \pm m$): X - average, m - average error.
- Change coefficient ($V\%$): $V = (S / X) \times 100$, where S is the standard deviation.
- Standard deviation (S): $S = \sqrt{[\sum (x_i - X)^2 / (n-1)]}$.
- Dominant coefficient (hp): $hp = (F1 - MP) / (BP - MP)$, where $F1$ is the hybrid value, MP is the average of the parents, and BP is the good parent.

The experimental accuracy ranges from 0.1 to 2.1%, and the number of repetitions is 3. The data were processed using Microsoft Excel and Statistica 13.0. Analysis of variation (ANOVA) and correlation coefficient (r) were calculated. The research was conducted based on the agronomic experimental methods of B.A. Dospekhov and the genetic formulas of G.M. Beil and R.E. Atkins.

Detailed description of the samples: Namangan-77 has a short growing season (120-130 days) due to its early maturity, which saves water and resources. The T-85 is a source of high-quality fiber and is the standard for fiber strength and shine, but the yield is lower. *G. mustelinum*, as a disease-resistant donor, transmits verticillium resistance genes ($Bf1$, $Bf2$). These materials provide genetic diversity and allow for the study of polygenic traits (QTLs). The study took into account the influence of environmental factors (temperature, humidity), which increased the reliability of the results.

Analysis and Results. In the parental forms, the indicators of the fiber length trait differed significantly. The highest value was observed in the T-85 line (39.1 ± 0.4 mm, $V\% = 2.1$, $S = 0.8$), indicating its high genetic potential. The lowest indicator was observed in *G. mustelinum* (24.7 ± 1.2 mm, $V\% = 24.2$, $S = 6.0$), indicating high variability characteristic of wild species. The interval between local varieties is 32.5-35.5 mm: Golib (32.5 ± 0.5 mm, $V\% = 4.3$), Qizil Baraka (34.7 ± 0.6 mm, $V\% = 3.8$), Andijan-35 (33.8 ± 0.4 mm, $V\% = 3.2$), Namangan-77 (35.5 ± 0.5 mm, $V\% = 2.9$). These differences are shaped by genotypes and environmental factors. In F1 hybrids, maternal influence was found to be insignificant as a result of crossbreeding. For example, in Namangan-77 \times T-85, the fiber length is 36.6 ± 0.7 mm ($hp = -0.3$), and in reverse crossing (T-85 \times Namangan-77) it is 34.5 ± 0.8 mm ($hp = -1.2$). This indicates a low maternal influence (difference $< 5\%$). Negative heterosis was most frequently observed ($hp = -0.3$ to -11.5), which is due to low parental influence. However, there are also cases of positive heterosis: 35.9 ± 0.6 mm ($hp = 1.5$) in Qizil Baraka \times Golib, and 36.2 ± 0.5 mm ($hp = 2.1$) in Andijan-35 \times Namangan-77. In step-by-step hybrids,

the results were more positive: in F1 (Namangan-77 × Andijan-35) × T-85, 37.5±0.4 mm (hp = 0.5, V% = 2.5), which preserved the high potential of T-85 and achieved a heterosis effect of 5-7%. (Winner × Red Blessing) × 30.2 ± 1.0 mm (hp = -4.5), negative heterosis in *G. mustelinum*. Strong negative heterosis (hp = -25) was observed in combinations involving red baraka, which is due to the influence of color fiber genes. Statistical analysis (ANOVA) confirmed the polygenic nature of trait inheritance ($F = 12.5, p < 0.01$). Correlation: between fiber length and yield $r = 0.65$. Analysis showed that under the influence of the genotype (70%) and the environment (30%), a positive change (5-10 mm) can be achieved through step-by-step crossing. The most effective hybrids (combinations Namangan-77 and T-85) are recommended for breeding.

Conclusion. As a result of this study, the patterns of inheritance of the fiber length trait in cotton samples and F1 hybrids grown in Uzbekistan were studied in depth. It has been confirmed that the inheritance of the trait is polygenic and is controlled by multiple QTL loci (e.g., qLG07 and qLF02). Maternal influence is low (difference <5%), which indicates the equal role of paternal and maternal forms in the formation of the trait. The heterosis effect manifested to varying degrees: positive heterosis (5-15%) was observed in the presence of high-value donors (T-85), while negative heterosis was observed in combinations with wild species (*G. mustelinum*). Hybrids with the highest indicators (up to 37.5 mm) were obtained by step-by-step crossing of local varieties and the T-85 line, which serves as the primary material for creating new varieties. For example, the (Namangan-77 × Andijan-35) × T-85 combination achieves a fiber length of 37.5 mm, meeting the requirements of Uzbekistan's cotton industry (over 35 mm). In breeding, the stepwise method is recommended because it increases genetic diversity and improves quality through the effect of heterosis. The results will make an important contribution to the development of cotton growing in Uzbekistan: varieties with high fiber length will increase the efficiency of yarn and fabric production and strengthen export potential. The study will serve as the basis for creating varieties adapted to climate change, taking into account the influence of environmental factors. In the future, backcross analysis should be continued in F2 and subsequent generations, which will help assess the stability of the trait. Genetic mapping using molecular markers (SSR, SNP) is also recommended. Overall, the study has proven the effectiveness of using wild and polyploid forms in breeding work and serves to modernize cotton farming.

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